

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN AFRICA: CHARISMATIC AND TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP

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Abstract: Charismatic leadership is a leadership method in which a leader uses personal charms and persuasions to inspire and motivate his/her subjects to achieve specific goals. Similarly, transformational leadership is a pragmatic leadership style that accommodates teamwork collaborations to engender an environment of invention, creation, initiation, and introduction of something new to move society forward. Leadership by example encourages well-rounded development. The problem that warrants this study is to establish the nexus between the charismatic-transformational leadership style and sustainable development. The objective of this study is to analyze the urgent need for charismatic and transformational leadership for sustainable development in Africa and to make it in the limelight. Many Africans are disgusted with their leaders. This is because most African leaders, with their leadership styles, have failed to deliver good governance that results in sustainable development. The method of this study is analysis. This study's findings reveal that leaders with charisma and transformational insightfulness, such as visionary thinking and strategic planning, are better disposed for effective leadership than others. In conclusion, the implication is that leadership is neither for everybody nor a do-or-die affair. This program is for those who have the requisite leadership intelligence, discipline, and willingness for selfless service. Finally, this study recommends pre-election debates for all Africans vying for political leadership to showcase their charisma and transformational viewpoints for pre-election appraisal by the electorates.

Keywords: Charisma, Development, Innovation, Leadership, Transformation.

Introduction

In every business enterprise, the manager is the dynamic and life-giving element. Without his transformational leadership skills and zeal, "the resources of production" remain at the level of resources and never become finished products. In a comparative economy, managers' quality and performance determine the success of a business; indeed, they determine its survival. The only effective advantages any enterprise in a comparative economy can have are the quality and performance of its managers (Drucker, 1954, 3). Similarly, the quality and performance of every leader determine the level of development of society and the people who are led.

Many African countries are far from sustainable development mainly because their leaders lack charismatic and transformational leadership capacity. Their minds are set primarily on acquiring political power, using the power of incumbency to perpetually consolidate it, and enjoying the dividends that accrue from it. Some African leaders believe that sustainable development will enlighten the people to contest their political positions. Therefore, they consider it better for their subjects to remain in bondage, while they remain in power to lord it over them. It may be surprising to hear, but it is true that Uganda has never had a peaceful transition of power since its independence from British rule in 1962. Changes in leadership have been marked by coups, violence, or heavily contested election-results, rather than peaceful democratic transition. From Edward Mutesa II to Milton Obote, then to Idi Amin Dada, down to the incumbent Yoweri Museveni, who has been the 9th President of Uganda since 26th January, 1986, over 40 years of being in power as of 2026, there is no indication that he is leaving office soon (Horvitz and Catherwood, 2006, 438-439).

Nigeria's neighbor, Cameroon, is not even better politically than Uganda. President Paul Biya (born February 13, 1933, now 93) was the Prime Minister of Cameroon from 1975 to 1982, with Ahmadou Ahidjo as President from 1960 to 1982. Sequel to Ahidjo's unexpected resignation in 1982, Biya has been the 2nd president of Cameroon since November 6, 1982. He uses autocratic leadership style, human rights abuses, and suppression of political oppositions to perpetuate his power. How can sustainable development be achieved in a country with a leader with such a tireless autocratic leadership style? In Togo too, the Togolese leader, Faure Gnassingbe, is facing international criticism for his authoritarian style of leadership and even for remaining in power in the first place. He assumed office immediately after his father, Etienne Gnassingbe Eyadema, died in 2005. Eyadema seized power after leading a military coup in 1967 and remained in power until his death in 2005. For almost 38 years, he ruled Togo and imposed a one-party system. He amended the constitution to exterminate the term limit to remain in power. The worrisome issue is that these countries have presidents and not kings; therefore, they do not practice monarchy. Undoubtedly, when the so-called leaders obtain their mandate through scandalous election manipulations, the resultant effect is turning attention away from the people's sustainable development. The next section provides the details.

The Concept of Sustainable Development

The concept of development is sufficiently complex to resist an outright or straightaway definition. Therefore, it is embedded with many meanings. It can mean a process by which an inner principle comes to the spotlight while being hidden. It may be a slow, bit-by-bit transformation. A qualitative change or transformation that moves from the uninformed and less determined to the informed and fully determined. At this juncture, these several meanings of *development* are not necessarily exclusive. Many of them can be achieved together in a concrete process called development (Brugger, 1972, 92; Izunwa, 2009, 22-23). Development, in its general definition, is related to the conscious and positive change or transformation of a society and its people. *The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Politics* (2009) defines development as the "fulfillment of the necessary conditions for the realization of the potential of human personality" In its easiest and most elementary form, development is the increasing realization and satisfaction of people's fundamental necessities of life. It is constantly improving people's general standard of living over a long period of time. Development is not a short process. It is a lifelong process that is not limited to any age or period. It is an advancement process influenced by many biological and environmental factors in all areas of life.

In *Peace, Security, and Development in Nigeria*, Albert *et al.*, point out that “development is not only restricted to the concept of modernization where there are chains of industries, good road networks, beautiful urban development, and so forth.” If all these are achieved and yet, the greater mass of the populace still remains malnourished, illiterate, unemployed, unhealthy, and generally poor, it means that such a country is not yet developed”.

Again, the authors go on to say that “if there is the presence of infrastructural development, and yet there is no discipline and respect for the rule of law in the polity, such a country is still not developed” (2012, 33). Therefore, development is not one-sided. It is all-embracing and all-inclusive. One cannot say that Nigeria is developed just because its government officials go on private jets. The fact remains that many Nigerians are living in abject poverty. Development is neither sudden nor a hit-and-run game. It is a gradual process. It is a bit-by-bit or step-by-step change from one level to a better one in the society; development that can be sustained.

Therefore, sustainable development is a method or approach to growth and human development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future and unborn generations to meet their own needs. The main objective is to have a society where living conditions and resources meet human needs without counteracting, subverting, or weakening planetary integrity. In New York in 2015, the United Nations adopted the Seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as a blueprint, design, or pattern to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all. The following are the SDGs that, in my opinion, every African leader needs to pay serious attention to for sustainable development in his own country:

- ❖ **No Poverty:** End poverty in all its ramifications everywhere.
- ❖ **Zero Hunger:** End hunger, achieve food security, improve nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture.
- ❖ **Good health and Well-being:** Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all.
- ❖ **Quality Education:** Guarantee quality education for all students.
- ❖ **Gender Equality:** Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.
- ❖ **Clean Water and Sanitation:** Ensure sustainable management of water and sanitation for all.
- ❖ **Affordable and Clean Energy:** Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all.
- ❖ **Decent Work and Economic Growth:** Promote sustainable and inclusive economic growth and productive employment for all.
- ❖ **Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure:** Build resilient and high-spirited infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization, and promote innovation.
- ❖ **Reduced Inequalities:** Reduce inequalities within and among countries.
- ❖ **Sustainable Cities and Communities:** Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, and resilient.
- ❖ **Responsible Consumption and Production:** Ensure sustainable production and consumption patterns.
- ❖ **Climate Action:** Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
- ❖ **Life below water:** Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources.
- ❖ **Life on land:** Protect, restore and promote the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and reverse land degradation and biodiversity loss.

❖ **Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions:** Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all, and build effective, accountable, and inclusive institutions at all levels.

❖ **Partnerships for all Goals:** Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize global partnerships for sustainable development.

African leaders should search everywhere in taking concrete actions to drive progress towards realizing the ambitious 2030 Agenda set by the United Nations for Sustainable Development. Africa, as an Old World continent like Asia and Europe, should not be lagging behind even the New World Continents: North and South America. Therefore, bringing an end to poverty and hunger, increasing investments in rural infrastructure, promoting economic growth, easy access to energy and water, and improving education, healthcare system, water, and sanitation are key areas that are demanding urgent attention from African leaders.

The Concept of Leadership

“Leadership” covers various meanings. Fundamentally, the term means the state or position of being a leader. It is a process of directing, guiding, or influencing people to act in a particular manner to achieve specific goals (Anyaorah, 2017, 1). It has to do with inspiring confidence and trust to ensure maximum cooperation from the people under a leader’s control. It is also a process by which a person influences others to achieve or attain an objective. It is a way of directing an organization or society in a manner that makes it easier and more coherent to accomplish the course of action. The dividing line is: a leader should have some distinguishing character traits from the common folks (Iheanacho and Onyeka, 2017).

Therefore, in accordance with this mindset, a leader is someone who influences people’s behavior either consciously or unconsciously to make them attain set goals. What a good leader and a good manager do is not the same. For instance, leaders are efficient advocates for followers and care about them. Leaders build trust, innovate, give an exact description of the present, paint a good picture of the future, and act with integrity and competence. While a good manager does things right, a good leader does the right things (Bennis and Goldsmith, 2003; Anyaorah, 2017, 1). Leadership, as already mentioned, is a process that may be identified as a series of ways that will affect leadership styles.

The Concept of Charismatic Leadership

The English word *charisma* is a direct transliteration of the original Ancient Greek word *χάρισμα*, which denotes a gift of grace or favor freely given to a particular person for the good of others. This singular term and its plural term *χαρίσματα* (*charimata*) are both derived from the Greek word *χάρις* (*charis*), which means grace and charm. The charm referred to here is not magic. According to *The New International Webster’s Comprehensive Dictionary of the English Language: The Encyclopedic Edition*, “charisma is the aggregate of those special gifts of mind and character, which are the source of the personal power of exceptional individuals, and upon which they depend for their capacity to secure the allegiance of, and exercise decisive authority over, large masses of people.”

Charismatic leadership is, therefore, a leadership style marked by the leader’s ability to use his or her gift of the gab, communication skills, persuasive acumen, and personal charm to influence and inspire others, especially followers, subjects, those placed under his leadership, and those who look up to him. Max Weber (1947) points out in *The Theory of Social and Economic Organization* that charismatic leadership derives its authority and legitimacy from the leader’s real exceptional characteristics, not from formal rules or traditional customs.

Building on Weber's concept in enunciating a theory of charismatic leadership, Conger and Kanungo (1998) explicate that charismatic leadership is epitomized by four major characteristics: (i) possessing and articulating a vision; (ii) willing to take risks to actualize the vision; (iii) exhibiting or showing sensitivity to followers' needs; and (iv) demonstrating or displaying novel behavior.

Many scholars on charismatic leadership have deliberately avoided or shunned Weber's view that charismatic leaders are scarce, uncommon, and extraordinary. For instance, Conger (1989) argues that charisma is not a magical ability that is limited to some people. In this regard, Judge *et al.* (2006) pose a very pertinent question: "If charisma is seen as relatively prosaic, have we damaged the concept?" The authors go on to say: "clearly, the charismatic qualities of political leaders from Lincoln to Hitler, religious leaders from Martin Luther to Pope John Paul II, and business leaders from Estee Lauder to Jack Welch, do not seem to be a general commodity." It has been mentioned that charismatic leadership is a leadership approach marked by the leader's ability to influence and inspire others through his gift of the gab and his communication skills, persuasive acumen, and personal charm. Immediately after the publicly conducted Presidential Debate against the November 2024 US Presidential Election between President Joe Biden and the former President, Donald Trump, that took place on 27th June, 2024, at CNN's Studios in Atlanta, many Republicans began calling on President Biden to drop his second term presidential ambition because he mumbled some words and was not very articulate during his debate with Trump. This is just *the tip of the iceberg* of how Americans generally frown at leadership without charisma.

Unfortunately, in Africa, no one stresses on pre-election leadership or presidential debates because those in office believe that they will always have their way, willy-nilly. Should Africans continue to maintain the ugly *status quo*? Pre-election debates are veritable avenues through which the people or the electorates make their appraisal of those who desire to become their leaders. Through these debates, those vying for the oval office demonstrate and showcase their charisma and transformational viewpoints, paving the way for the electorates to make their pre-election judgments.

The Concept of Transformational Leadership

Transformative leadership supplements charismatic leadership, making its positive effects more realistic in people's lives and society in general. In *Leadership and Performance beyond Expectations*, Bernard Bass argues that transformational leadership is achieved through the four "I's": idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration. Idealized influence is displayed whenever the transformational leader makes visible or obvious charisma that the followers consider worth imitation. Transformational leaders promote and nurture inspirational motivation by articulating inspiring visions to their subjects. Intellectual stimulation is engendered when transformational leaders stimulate the innovative or creative skills of followers through stimulating questions and challenges. Finally, having a good and very sincere down-to-earth listening ear to attend to the individual needs of the subjects gives transformative leaders the opportunity to advance and promote individual consideration.

Therefore, the transformational style of leadership focuses on exalting, ennobling, inspiring, and motivating followers to attain higher levels of performance and personal growth. Transformative leadership involves creating a vision for the future, communicating that vision in a compelling way, and empowering and supporting others to work towards that vision (Ibe and Tiger, 2024, 182). As a very peculiar and unique leadership style, "transformative leadership ... is concerned with emotions, values, ethics, standards, and long-

term goals and includes accessing people's motives, satisfying their needs, and treating them as full human beings. It involves an exceptional form of influence that moves followers to accomplish more than what is usually expected of them" (Osuji, Okoroafor and Oji, 2021, 15). It animates, enlivens, and invigorates followers to achieve unexpected results, even beyond their perceived capabilities. Transformational leaders empower their followers to work harder and make independent decisions regarding their personal and professional development. This is the type of leadership style needed for sustainable development in Africa.

The Nexus between Charismatic and Transformational Leadership for Sustainable Development

Harmonizing charismatic and transformational leadership styles is crucial for Africa's sustainable development. Charismatic leaders animate, revivify, and unify their followers through their awe-inspiring visions and ingratulatory abilities, while transformational leaders increase their followers' confidence to realize unexpected results through exceptional performance. The ability of African leaders to coalesce and blend these two leadership approaches can be a powerful means for attaining sustainable development in the continent.

Charismatic leaders are skilled at compellingly transmitting thoughts and feelings and invigorating their followers to achieve their ultimate potentials. Through their charisma, they bring forth cohesive and loyal followers. On the other hand, transformational leaders put the overall growth and development of their subjects first. Transformational leadership has been associated with business, entrepreneurship, and school development, as it is incumbent upon managers, caretakers, and teachers to work hard. Therefore, African leaders imbibing a leadership style that harmonizes the elements of charisma and transformation can be a powerful approach that yields the desired and long-awaited results.

Mission and Vision: Charismatic and Transformational Leadership for Sustainable Development in Africa

The English word "mission" is derived from the Latin noun *missio*, *-onis*; also *missus*, which is the past participle of the infinitive of the verb *mittere* meaning "to send" Therefore, the English word "mission" has to do with sending someone or something to accomplish a particular purpose(s). Hence, the English words: missionary, messenger, and even missile. The English word "vision" is derived from the Latin noun *visio*, *-onis*; also *visus*, which is the past participle of the infinitive of the verb *videre* meaning "to see." Actually, the Latin word *video* means "I see" (*The New International Webster's Comprehensive Dictionary of the English Language: Encyclopedic Edition*, 2004). From the above-mentioned perspectives, African leaders should always realize that they are on a mission, sent and authorized by the people to achieve specific goals. In addition, they should be cognizant of the fact that they cannot achieve sustainable development for the people they represent without foresight. The anticipation of a mission and vision for sustainable development is that moment in charismatic and transformational leadership when leadership dynamics unavoidably take center stage. African leaders should have a clear sense of direction to avoid men who are blind from leading and directing sighted people.

Charismatic and transformational leaders develop mission-oriented statements or questions such as, "Where did we come from?" This is a question of history and legacy. What are the issues that really matter to us? This is a question of values. What do we do? This is a question of range and type of task ahead. How do we do it? This is a question of the specific ways we make or create values and achieve them. The clear, coherent, and sincere articulation of these mission-oriented questions gives the transformational leader a sense of direction, guidance, and steering. The loss of a sense of direction or the development of hollow and futile systems in leadership

styles deadens and dampens the followers or makes them cynical and taunting; if to an unbearable extent, they can become disloyal, insubordinate, and rebellious. However, the masses forge a fundamental relationship to one another created by service to a common cause (Morrill, 2010, 137-138).

However, the fundamental idea of vision at the heart of charismatic and transformational leadership is not cabalistic or esoteric. Concerning identity, we enquire: “who are we?” and concerning mission, we wonder: “why do we exist?” In terms of vision, it is very crucial we query: “to what do we aspire?” Because human life and the tenure of each person’s leadership are limited, African leaders should seek achievements that will endure and stand the test of time. Visions that chip in to the tasks of charismatic and transformational leadership are not only ambitious but also credible. In being inspirational, it defines attractive possibilities, and in being realistic, it is seen as attainable over a period of time (Morrill, 142).

Therefore, African leaders can build their capacity to foresee the future by imbibing these two essential qualities: (i) imagining the possibilities: Charismatic transformational leaders are possibility thinkers who focus on making positive changes. (ii) Enkindling a common purpose: These leaders find a common purpose by ascertaining what is purposeful to others. People desire to go after leaders they believe can see beyond present challenges and visualize a more glorious future for them.

Conclusions and Recommendations

From ancient times, leadership never ceases but only takes new forms and advances new values. Therefore, this research has argued that sustainable development is possible and achievable in Africa if the people elected into leadership positions have charisma and transformational ideas that engender innovations and inventions. A close link exists between sustainable development and charismatic transformational approaches to leadership efficacy. The paradigm of charismatic and transformational leader is Ronald Reagan, the 40th American President (1981-1989), and the greatest performer ever to occupy the White House. His wonderful economic policies, “Reaganomics”, achieved several key milestones in American history. Again, his powerful communication skills earned him the title “the Great Communicator;” not minding that he told the Americans: “do not call me ‘the Great Communicator’, but rather call me ‘the Communicator of Great Things.’” His remarkable oratory and policies contributed significantly to the demise of Soviet Communism and the fall of the Berlin Wall in November 1989 (McKenna, 2010, 265266).

Reagan’s motivational speeches and star performances were his essential link to the mass of voters who liked him personally. According to James Reston, “President Reagan has a story for every occasion and a reasonable excuse for every disaster” (Podell and Anzovin, 2001: 869). He would insert a story or anecdote based on his personal experience to convey his message, analyzing even the most abstract issues in terms of his own feelings, experience, capacity for growth, and so on. This had the wonderful and useful effect of making his speeches seem more like intimate conversation with a friend than an expression of policy by the most powerful man in the world. According to Alexander Haig, Reagan’s first Secretary of State, “one key to Reagan’s success was the impression he gives to liking the audience he is talking to; so, most audiences could not help but like him back” (Podell and Anzovin, 869).

Conversely, one of the paradigms of sit-tight and visionless leadership is what is happening in Cameroon. President Biya is the oldest serving ruler and is among the longest serving heads of state globally, excluding monarchs. In the 2025 presidential election on October 12, the then 92-year-old Biya was reelected, “securing”

53.66 percent of the vote; while his main challenger and former ally, Issa Tchiroma Bakary, came second with 35.19 percent of the vote.

The opposition leaders challenged the truth or validity of Biya's victory, and made heavy allegations of electoral malpractice. Several Cameroonians refused to accept the results. Regardless of these allegations, Biya was sworn in for his eighth consecutive seven-year term in office on November 6, 2025, thereby, extending his presidency to 2032, when he will be 100 years old. He has unrelentingly held onto power for more than 4 decades. Even before the election last year, many Cameroonians were reportedly reluctant to register as voters because they believed that it would be a waste of time. However, they were fully aware that Biya planned, as usual, to rig the election in his favor. (*The Guardian*, August 22, 2024). Leaders who force themselves on the people are not there for the good of the people. In real democracy, leadership is truly won, not grabbed or seized.

Therefore, the saying: "a person is what he or she thinks" is always true. Africa needs charismatic leaders with transformational mindsets. Values are not poured into human beings from without, but are generated from within. It is all about people who have the necessary capacities to occupy vital leadership positions. Kouzes and Posner (2010) outline five practices for leadership effectiveness in *A Coach's Guide to Developing Exemplary Leaders*, which, in my opinion would be of great help for African leaders. They include:

(i) **Modeling the Way:** African leaders should be cognizant of the fact that to get dedication and loyalty from their subjects, they need to be good exemplars of the behaviors they expect of others. Leaders who lead by example create situations that make it simple to have unanimity on shared values.

(ii) **Inspiring a Shared Vision:** Here, vision refers to a common dream of the future. It is not about making statements. Charismatic and transformational leaders visualize the desired future. They get their subjects behind the vision by clearly and realistically evincing their passion. They strongly believe that they can change the *status quo* for the good of all.

(iii) **Challenging the Process:** Transformational and charismatic leaders seek ways to amend processes for better outputs. They challenge themselves and their subjects and take risks to innovate advancement ideas and mindsets. They learn from their fumbles and failures, and even their achievements and triumphs, making it very likely that their subjects will follow in their footsteps.

(iv) **Enabling others to act:** Very obviously and truly, leaders with observable charismatic and transformational qualities nurture coactions and teamwork through interpersonal skills. When leaders address their subjects with dignity and respect, it will help build confidence in the subjects to take teamwork seriously. It empowers the people.

(v) **Encouraging the heart:** Transformational leaders with charisma bring hope, trust, and gratification to the people. They exhibit confidence in the good actions of the individuals. People will strive to attain unimaginable heights when they realize that their leaders care and value their commitment (Kouzes and Posner, 6-9). The sky is the limit for Africans when they notice that their leaders appreciate their genuine efforts and are making judicious use of the humongous resources at their disposal.

Therefore, African leaders should consider that it is incumbent on them to deliver sustainable development to their people. After their observations in *Ecclesia in Africa* that Africa is a huge continent where diverse situations are found, the Synod Fathers sadly have to say: "One common situation, without any doubt, is that Africa is full of problems. Abject poverty, tragic mismanagement of available resources, political instability,

and social disorientation occur in almost all our nations.” They go further to compare Africa to the man who went from Jerusalem to Jericho; “he fell among robbers who stripped him, beat him and departed, leaving him half dead (cf. Lk 10: 30-37). Africa is a continent where countless human beings, men and women, children, and young people, are lying on the edge of the road, sick, injured, disabled, marginalized, and abandoned. “They are in dire need of Good Samaritans who will come to their aid” (John Paul II, *Ecclesia in Africa*, 1995, Sections 40 & 41).

In Nigeria, many groups mapped out some days from August 1, 2024, for a nationwide protest to demonstrate their grievances against the harsh economic policies of the government that have opened doors for: high costs of petrol pump price, high inflation rates, high costs of food commodities, high interest rates and cost of governance, insecurity, and so on. Unfortunately, government-sponsored thugs, who targeted protesters, marred the proposed protest. Leaders who apply the right policies obtain the right results that would benefit all members of the society. Unquestionably, leadership is not for everybody. According to Plato, only a few people have the requisite intelligence and discipline for such a position. Plato manifests his idealism and its political consequences in the *Republic*. He imagines a society whose elite would study philosophy and attain enlightenment. Then, they would understand the vanity of political ambition but would nevertheless accept the responsibility of governing the people under their care. Plato never precisely clarifies the reason they should accept this responsibility. However, a critical and prudent mind would see Plato’s consideration of the leaders’ responsibilities to their states as obvious (Noble *et al.*, 1998, 109). Therefore, leadership should not be a “do-or-die-affair” as some African leaders perceive it. It is a call to duty.

Finally, it has already been pointed out that pre-election debates are reliable avenues through which the people appraise the capacities of those who desire to become their leaders. It is through these debates that those vying for the oval office showcase their charisma and transformational viewpoints to the electorates before the election. This is one of the easiest and surest ways to get those who have leadership capacities into leadership positions and hold them accountable if they do not fulfill the promises they made before the election. There is no doubt that Africans are already tired of visionless leaders who do not have every sense of assignment and mission. Once the majority of African countries have quality leaders with charismatic, transformational, and innovative mindsets, sustainable development is assured.

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